

A Correlational Study Between Parental Praise and Types of Mindsets in order to Enhance Young Learners in the 21st Century

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Abstract:- Nowadays, there are various ways to praise a child, which vary from family to family. Thus, it can affect a child's mindset. Parental Praise can be classified into two types: Process Praise, which is praised for the effort that is put into accomplish a task, and the other type is Person Praise which is praised for the ability to accomplish a task. A person's mindset is the set of mental attitudes held by someone who performs their skills and abilities, which can be classified into two types: a fixed mindset, in which both skills and abilities are innate and cannot be improved; and the other type is a growth mindset, in which both skills and abilities can be developed through learning, experience, and effort. Therefore, the purpose of this research is to investigate the causal relationship between Person Praise and Process Praise and Dweck's Mindset Theory. An online questionnaire with 12 closed-ended statements based on a 5-Likert scale was developed, representing Person Praise and Parental Praise influencing characteristics of the two mindset types. A total of 150 voluntary responses were received. The analysis supported the theoretical frameworks that there was a moderate positive correlation between compliments on effort and a growth mindset ($r = 0.56$). However, this research showed that there was no correlation between a process praise and a fixed mindset. Based on this research, there is liable to have a improvable characteristics, there needs to have a presence of process praise and supportive environmental for their effort. Thus, we should focus on praising on children on effort more than intelligence, in order to encourage them to seek out challenges and the opportunity to develop skills and abilities that they are really interested in. In conclusion a children with a process praise would likely to have a better learning performance.

Keywords:- Person Praise; Parental Praise; Fixed mindset; Growth mindset; Learning performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, Improvement is one of the essential characteristics which individuals with these characteristics are more suitable for the 21st century. Originally, Dweck's mindset theory explained that one's belief in their effort is about flexibility to acquire new knowledge and the other belief is in their intelligence. In other words, this type of mindset is to prove successfulness, smartness, talent, and righteousness (Dweck, 2006). Recently, some researchers

believe that parental praise explains the way that parent praise their children because this action can influence their children's mindset. Through all the research, few attempts have been made about the correlation of these two frameworks to understand daily life experiences based on a theoretical point of view and a lack of solid findings. Therefore the hypothesis in this research was regraded both theoretically and statistically. The topic is focused on young learners learning performance and how they react to difficult tasks, which refer to their mindset.

Additionally, it seems to be influenced by the way parents praise them. It can be a process praise or person praise. After the theoretical discussion and descriptive statistics, a correlational examination is performed to provide solid evidence of some aspects of these two frameworks regarding other. This research can raise awareness among parents or teachers about how to praise their children, which can encourage them to grow a positive or negative mindset in the long term.

➤ *Mindset*

Mindset is a set of mental attitudes and individual construct to respond or to interpret under a circumstances. The mentality hypothesis examines individuals' attitudes to problems and explains why some people get disheartened by failure or withdraw when confronted with hurdles (Dweck, 1986). Fixed mentality (entity theory) and development mindset (incremental theory) are the two primary categories of people's beliefs about their intellect or academic aptitude levels (Dweck et al., 1995). On the one hand, growth mindset is a person who believes that hard work and good strategies can surpass thing that they do. They also believe that their talent can be improve by hard working. Growth mindset' person careless about looking smart, they concern about how to develop themselves and put a lot of effort on it (Carol Dweck, 2016). The examination of people with growth mindset is when they know that they can be smarter than before by study and practice, they will be fascinating in it. People with growth mindset usually have a normal phases such as "I think I can do it if I put a lot of effort on it" or "Experiencing of failure make me become better". They think more positive than fixed mindset people which can make them become easier to improve their intelligences. On the other hand, individuals who develop a fixed mindset believe that their skills and abilities cannot be improved and their intelligence, which they believe is innate. Therefore, they would likely avoid challenges, desire to look smart, ignore feedback, and are more likely to see the arduous task as an

intellectual indicator. Furthermore, for that, they would construct a negative thoughts to lower their intellectual confidence. For instance, a common phrase such as “I am no good at this thing, it is no good for me to try” and “I am not built for this and will never do it right.” Due to the phrases mentioned above, the example may lead them in a way that lacks skills and abilities.

➤ *Parental Praise*

Parental praise is a factor that can motivate children and bolster their self-confidence of children (Hae In Lee et al., 2016). There is many circumstances in that parent can praise their child. Firstly, praise their child when they accomplish the task and do not give enough attention to the process that may not be the problem. However, if their child fails in some task, they might believe that they were born without talent, unable to complete this task, or unworthy (Corpus & Lepper, 2007). In addition, if parents praise the behavior or effort of their child and give any attention to what their child has been doing or the processing of their work, that can lead their child to know how important effort is and can see the link between success and work hard (Gunderson et al., 2013), this type of praise is called Process praise. To be more precise, the person that grows with person praise might have fewer resilience skills than the person that grows with process praise because their receive the compliment only when they complete or achieve a task, but if they fail, they do not get a compliment for what they have been doing.

II. THEORETIC FRAMEWORK

According to previous information passages, we hypothesized that children who grew up with process praise could develop a Growth Mindset. On the other hand, children that grew up with Person praise from their parents could lead to a Fixed mindset.

To be more precise, Person praise makes their child believe that they are born with or without ability. This leads to the fixed mindset theory, in which the result is that children might put effort as much as they can into the task that they think they are unsuitable for. In other words, Process praise makes their child believe that they can do it or be improved if they put much effort into it and keep trying to do better. The mindset of the previous statement is the Growth mindset (Gunderson et al., 2013).

Therefore, we want to investigate the causal relationship between Person Praise and Process Praise and Dweck's Mindset Theory.

III. METHODOLOGY

Residents of Thailand received the self-administered online questionnaire that we disseminated. A total of 150 survey responses were received, which consisted of 0.7%, 14%, 68.7%, 6%, and 10.7% survey respondents in various age groups from under 10, 10-12, 13-15, 16-18, 19-21, and above 21 years old, respectively. In the current circumstance of the COVID-19 pandemic, our research collected data from survey respondents, which was a straightforward and appropriate method. Before starting with their online response, the respondents were informed about the study's goal and given informed consent.

A total of 12 questionnaire statements were used in our study, all of which were closed-ended 5-point Likert-type scales ranging from strongly agree (scale 1) to disagree (scale 5) strongly.

The statements were classified into four categories (two for each), enclosing Growth mindset (GM), Fixed mindset (FM), Parental praise on intelligence (PP-I), and Parental praise on effort (PP-E).

The statements and their corresponding categories are shown in Table 1. To avoid the demand for characteristics being produced, the sequence of these assertions was rearranged. Respondents were required to select just one of five scales that best reflected their degree of agreement to finish the survey.

The online survey was terminated after the total number of replies reached 150. The data were analyzed through descriptive statistics, which employed mean scores and standard deviation values to show how the data was distributed.

The averages of the statements in the same category were then used to examine the correlation between the categories. The interpretation of correlation coefficients was based on Mukaka (2012), in which figures between 0.3 and 0.5 present weak correlation, between 0.5 and 0.7 present moderate correlation, between 0.7 and 0.9 present strong correlation, and those above 0.9 present robust correlation. While those figures under 0.3 are considered negligible correlation. Nevertheless, if suitable, this study highlights a probable trend of connected variables, even if the values are less than 0.3 for discussion purposes, without intending to generalize the findings.

Table 1 : Parental praise and mindset questionnaire items

No.	Statement	Category identified
1	I become confident in my ability when other people tell me that I can overcome challenges by working hard.	PP-E
2	I become confident in my ability when other people tell me to improve on something.	GM
3	I become confident in my ability when other people compliments on my achievement.	PP-I
4	I willing to give up when I consider that myself do not good enough for the task.	FM
5	I become confident when someone praises me by effort.	PP-E
6	When I see successful people, I believe that you can succeed as same as those people.	GM
7	I become confident in my ability when other people tell me that I am good for this task	PP-I
8	I become insecure in my ability when I have to do certain task that I know I am not capable of	FM
9	I believe that I can improve myself if parent praises to my attempt.	PP-E
10	I believe that I can accomplish a certain task when I try my best.	GM
11	My parent only praise you because of your successful achievement.	PP-I
12	I am not willing to do certain task that I am not good at.	FM

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IV. RESULT & DISCUSSION

According to Table 2. The data demonstrates that the average scores of growth mindset, fixed mindset, process praise, and person praise were 3.99, 3.20, 4.22, and 3.99, respectively. To be more precise, there was a slightly different between growth mindset and person praise, about 0.004, which we considered negligible.

Table 2 : Average figures results based on the parental praise and mindset questionnaires (N=150)

	Category	Mean
1	Growth mindset	3.99
2	Fixed mindset	3.20
3	Process praise	4.22
4	Person praise	3.99

It is apparent among the 150 respondents that the figures for process praise are greater than those from person praise significantly, as well as the difference between growth mindset and fixed mindset, which those figures of growth mindset were more significant than those fixed mindsets as it reflects that the greater the level of growth mindset the better learning performance learners are more likely accomplish. In addition, they tend to be determined and dedicated to working against difficulties and are likely to focus on solving the tricky challenges more significantly than fixed mindset learners would (Dweck, 2009).

According to Table 3, statistical examination to indicate the degree of correlation reveals a moderate positive correlation between growth mindset and process praise. Likewise, the correlation between the fixed mindset and process praise presented a weak positive correlation. Therefore, this result supports the theoretical framework (described in section 2). Create empirical evidence of process praise and growth mindset from the analysed perspective. If

people with this mindset confront the challenges that they have a similar set of abilities to tackle, they will be able to tackle them better than the former because they have developed the skill to handle them. This can be interpreted as individuals being exposed to more opportunities for mistakes as a result of experiencing particular challenges on their own, allowing them to learn how to improve and overcome these challenges, resulting in the development of a growth mindset in which they believe-ability and skills are malleable and accept feedback for improvement (Bandura, 1982a; Dweck, 2006).

Therefore, recommendations can be made to both parents and teachers who can potentially establish children’s mindsets. This, however, must be centered on their attempt to complete assigned tasks rather than their level of intelligence. Furthermore, they must reflect on receiving certain remarks that will help them improve while excluding other types of comments that will cause them to accept compliments on intellect.4.

Table 3 : Correlation coefficients based on the parental praise and mindset questionnaires (N=150)

Category	GM	FM
PP-E	0.560	0.280
PP-I	0.005	0.114

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, statistical approaches investigated the association between parental praise (person and process praise) and mindset types (growth and fixed mindset). The study's findings, based on a statistical approach and 150 respondents, provide evidence to establish the link between parental and mindset types. There was a moderate correlation between a growth mindset and process praise ($r = 0.56$) even though the correlations between a fixed mindset and process praise were negligible ($r = 0.28$), as were the correlations between a fixed mindset and person praise ($r = 0.114$). However, there was no correlation between a growth mindset and person praise ($r = 0.005$). This research can recommend that both parents and teachers be aware of how to praise their learners, which can influence their children's mindset. To be more precise, if parents praise their children using process praise, this might develop a growth mindset. However, if parents praise their children using a person, their mindset might be developed into a fixed mindset.

First and foremost, a fixed mindset driven by intelligence-based reward rather than effort-based recognition would have repercussions. For example, children's learning capacities may exhibit less progress due to avoiding obstacles that lead to stagnation, as well as their assumption that their talents and abilities are innate and cannot be improved. Finally, process praising may inspire a youngster to learn new things, not be scared to fail, and continually strive for better. As a result, the children are more likely to perform well in the tasks that they received.

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